

D1.2 Annual report on the activities of the Platform (ExCo, AHM, monthly meeting, ad-hoc meeting)

Tier: Technology

Priority Area: Training Platform

ELIXIR Commissioned Service Report for Deliverables/Milestones

Document info

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0.1	Fotis Psomopoulos	2026/01/22	First draft
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	Admin Check by Hub (CoS Portfolio Manager)		
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Executive Summary

The deliverable consists of a comprehensive description of the key outcomes of the Training Platform during 2025 for inclusion in the ELIXIR Annual Report.

Document info

Responsible Participant	GR-INAB/CERTH
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Author List

Node	Institution	Name, surname	ORCID
GR-Greece	CERTH	Fotis, Psomopoulos	0000-0002-0222-4273
ES-Spain	BSC	Eva, Alloza	0000-0001-8385-9336
CH-Switzerland	UU	Jessica, Lindvall	0000-0002-5042-8481
BE - Belgium	SIB	Geert, van Geest	

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Annual Report of the Training Platform activities

Training - 2025

<p>Authors/Pref erred Contacts</p>	<p>Platform co-leads and Hub Platform Coordinators: Jessica Lindvall (SE) Fotis Psomopoulos (GR) Eva Alloza (ES) Katharina Heil (Hub) Mihail Anton (Hub)</p>
<p>Number of Services</p>	<p>Number of Platform services: 36</p>
<p>Content <500 words</p>	<p>Aims/purpose of the Platform (one sentence): The main mission of the Training Platform (TrP) is to build and promote standards for training, and with this support align to the training efforts and activities of the ELIXIR Nodes, establishing concrete synergies across the European and global training ecosystem.</p> <p>Any changes in co-leadership in 2025: <i>None</i></p> <p><u>Scientific Programme 2024-28</u> The 2024–28 Scientific Programme focused on consolidating the Platform's structure and aligning its strategic roadmap with the broader European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) context. Significant progress has been made in formalizing the Platform's governance, including the creation of first drafts for the Terms of Reference for both Training Coordinators and the Learning Paths Editorial Board. Furthermore, the Platform has started the work towards establishing a clear roadmap for ELIXIR Training Services towards 2028, amongst others, formalizing the Train the Trainer (TtT) programme as an integral part of the Training SPLASH portal.</p> <p>The programme also emphasized connecting ELIXIR Communities and Platforms, a goal advanced also through the dedicated All Hands Meeting (AHM) workshop. Finally, a key highlight activities included the formal incorporation of the FAIR Training Focus Group into the working group structure, ensuring FAIR principles are deeply embedded in the TrP activities.</p> <p><u>Platform Services</u> A major highlight for Platform Services for 2025 was the development and rollout of SPLASH, a centralized website designed to consolidate Training Platform outputs and services following the training life cycle. SPLASH was introduced to the Interoperability</p>

Platform during a meeting in April, and a dedicated communication kit is currently being prepared.

Concurrent work continues on the Training Metrics Database (TMD), which is undergoing testing for a new model, further pushed forward through a BioHackathon 2025 project to further its development.

The Platform is also consolidating standards and best practices for Open Science and Open Education. This includes generating an overview of critical network components for Training Coordinators (TrCs) and Node members. Additionally, new Standard Operating Procedures (SOPs) are being finalized, specifically for ELIXIR Lessons and the Learning Paths, ensuring a standardized integration into the training lifecycle.

EU projects

The Platform continues to maintain a strong presence in EU-funded projects. Highlight activities include platform members delivering teaching modules as part of the RltrainPlus project. The platform also supports training activities within the PHENET project and has actively engaged in training-related EC calls for 2026.

Collaborations within ELIXIR

Collaboration remains central to the Platform's success, as evidenced by a number of joint efforts with other Communities and Platforms. Notable is the AI Summer School 2025, led by ELIXIR-FR in partnership with ELIXIR-BE, ELIXIR-GR, and ELIXIR-CH that attracted more than 50 ELIXIR members to receive training in AI, from technologies to standards. A significant milestone was the launch of the ELIXIR-GOBLET Train-the-Trainer Mentorship program, with the first round involving four mentee Nodes and three mentor Nodes.

Coordination with the People and Node Tiers has been strengthened, specifically regarding the agenda for the joint annual meeting in Lisbon in March 2025. The platform also contributed to the BioHackathon, focusing on AI-ready metadata and the Biohackrxiv project. Knowledge sharing is maintained through monthly Programme Teleconferences, with scheduled presentations in 2025 covering FAIR training, the TMD, Training Certification, and the ELIXIR Learning Paths project.

Collaborations outside ELIXIR

The platform maintains robust international ties, continuing its strategic work with Australian BioCommons. The ongoing connection to GOBLET has been assessed and reaffirmed, ensuring global alignment on training standards. Furthermore, the platform was represented at the Global Bioinformatics Education Summit 2025, ensuring ELIXIR remains a key voice in the global bioinformatics education community.

Figure

Figure description: NA for now

Outcomes and expected impact

The deliverable comprehensively describes key outcomes of the Training Platform during 2025, as covered in the ELIXIR Annual Report.

Dissemination Plans

The ELIXIR Annual Report is a key document of the ELIXIR Hub and will thus be disseminated following ELIXIR Hub practices.